

Some Applications of Transition Matrices Via Eigen Values

Authors : Adil AL-Rammahi

Abstract : In this short paper, new properties of transition matrix were introduced. Eigen values for small order transition matrices are calculated in flexible method. For benefit of these properties applications of these properties were studied in the solution of Markov's chain via steady state vector, , and information theory via channel entropy. The implemented test examples were promised for usages.

Keywords : Eigen value problem, transition matrix, state vector; information theory

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014